

Closing Africa's Infrastructure Deficit: the Role of Gender Responsiveness in Urban Planning

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Abstract : As Africa becomes a global hotbed of better-quality road and rail networks, its cities are incisive about closing the infrastructure deficit in terms of coverage and access. This paper builds on survey and interview data amongst residents and planners in Kampala, to demonstrate how the principle gender responsiveness can be applied to urban planning processes to lessen the demand-side shortfalls in infrastructure across cities of Africa. During the study, women associated their demand for infrastructure with personal safety, hygiene and physical comfort whereas men were primarily concerned about public security, individual punctuality while on travel as well as convenience and quicker connectivity to public utilities. But planning by city authorities has not transcended the physical, economic and environmental accounts of urban service provision to include responsiveness to the gendered nature of infrastructure needs. Therefore improvements in city infrastructure are seldom aligned to variations in women's compared to men's infrastructure needs. The paper concludes with a step-wise framework for conceptualizing how urban planning can be gender responsive, together with examples on real-life applications for cities in Africa.

Keywords : infrastructure, gender responsiveness, urban planning, African cities

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